

The Romanian Electoral Management Body: Between the Governmental Model and the Independent Model

Daniel Buti¹ and Alexandru Radu²

Abstract

This study examines the Romanian Electoral Management Body (EMB), focusing on its dualistic structure. It distinguishes between the formal independence and functional independence of electoral management institutions and proposes a qualitative evaluation of the Permanent Electoral Authority (AEP) and the Central Electoral Bureau (BEC). The analysis is anchored in the context of the three EMB models, independent, governmental, and mixed, providing a framework for understanding the Romanian system. The findings indicate that the Romanian EMB exhibits formal independence but faces a political influence that cannot be neglected. The analysis employs the criteria proposed by Bishop and Hoeffler to evaluate the EMB's independence and impartiality. The study finds that two out of five criteria are fully met, two are only formally respected, and one is not met. This highlights a significant discrepancy between the formal and functional independence of the EMB, distancing it from the ideal independent model. While Romania formally adopted an independent EMB model, practical realities reveal a closer alignment with a governmental model, influenced by political and financial dependencies. The research observations can be used both to advance studies in this field and to propose recommendations for improving the legal and institutional framework with the aim of strengthening democracy and public trust in electoral processes

Keywords

elections; electoral integrity; election management body; institutional design; Romania

¹ Daniel Buti (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1291-577X>) is Lecturer at the National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA) in Bucharest. He has a PhD in Political Sciences and he published a series of books and scientific articles regarding the post-communist Romanian political system. His research interests include political parties and party systems, elections and electoral systems, democracy and public participation. Email: daniel.but@snsa.ro.

² Alexandru Radu is Professor at the National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA) in Bucharest. He published numerous studies, articles, and books on political analysis (political systems, party systems, electoral systems). His areas of interest include electoral systems, political parties and party systems, comparative politics.

Introduction

The Electoral Management Bodies (EMBs) are essential institutions responsible for organizing, overseeing, and certifying elections to ensure they are fair and free. They play a critical role in democracy by ensuring that all citizens have equal access to the vote and that its outcome, as well as the democratic process itself, is considered legitimate (López-Pintor, 2000; Elklit and Reynolds, 2005). However, because EMBs are so important, they can also be targets for actors who want to interfere with elections or manipulate the results (Birch, 2011). Consequently, the independence of EMBs is vital to protect them from political interference and ensure that they can carry out their duties impartially. This independence is an important factor in maintaining electoral integrity and preventing electoral fraud (Norris, 2015).

The performance of the EMB is defining for the "infrastructural capacity" of a state to run elections (Fortin-Rittberger, 2014; Zavadskaya and Garnett, 2018). A well-capacitated EMB fosters public trust by demonstrating its ability to manage electoral processes effectively and impartially. Thus, the quality of electoral governance significantly affects the integrity and legitimacy of elections (Hartlyn, McCoy and Mustillo, 2008). Effective EMBs ensure that electoral processes are transparent, accountable, and free from undue influence. Moreover, the conditions under which EMBs operate can greatly influence their effectiveness and the overall electoral integrity (Van Ham and Lindberg, 2015).

We define EMBs as organizations that are tasked with "managing some or all the elements that are essential for the conduct of elections" (Catt et al, 2014: 5). These essential elements include determining voter and candidate eligibility, conducting polling, and counting and validating votes. EMBs may also be responsible for voter registration, boundary delimitation, voter education and information, media monitoring and electoral dispute resolution.

Specifically, Mozaffar and Schedler (2002) outline three levels of electoral governance: rule making, rule application, and rule adjudication. Rule making involves setting rules for the election process, such as district magnitude, district boundaries, financial regulations or election observation. Rule application covers organizing the election, such as registering voters, candidates, and parties, as well as conducting voting and reporting results. Finally, rule adjudication involves certifying results and resolving disputes. The extent of an EMB's responsibility for these tasks depends on its design.

The design of EMBs varies from country to country and it depends primarily on democratic experience and political and cultural traditions (López-Pintor, 2000). Classical studies in this field primarily focus on the formal separation of EMBs from government authority (*de jure* independence). This gave rise to an influential tripartite classification of EMBs: independent, governmental, and mixed (Wall et al, 2006; Catt et al, 2014).

The independent model involves the existence of an EMB that operates as a fully autonomous entity, unaccountable to the executive branch of government. It may be accountable to the parliament, the judiciary, or the head of state. In general, autonomy is an essential criterion emphasized by the literature for free and fair elections (Lehoucq, 2002; Diamond and Morlino, 2004; Bishop and Hoeffler, 2016; Langford, Schiel and Wilson, 2021). On the contrary, the governmental model implies that elections are organized and managed within the framework of a government ministry (such as the Ministry of the Interior), either at the national or local level. As for the mixed model, it combines to different degrees elements of the two previous models. Thus, it requires the existence of a government institution responsible for the current operations related to the organization and management of the elections, doubled by an independent oversight body.

However, the formal independence of EMB does not always translate into functional independence on the ground. For instance, data indicates that only about 53% of states reporting

independent EMBs meet the standards for free and fair elections. These standards can be operationalized through the simultaneous application of the following criteria: "(a) Election boundaries are set up so that no candidate/party is favored (no gerrymandering) (de facto); (b) EMBs are held accountable to election law and abide by it; (c) EMBs are independent and impartial; (d) EMBs have sufficient time to organize elections (i.e. no snap election); (e) Decisions made by and complaints made to the EMBs are subject to review and possible reversal" (Bishop and Hoeffler, 2016).

Based on the criteria presented above, we analyze in this article the electoral management body in Romania to determine whether its independence is merely formal or also real and functional. The aim is to investigate the degree of autonomy of the EMB in the context of organizing and conducting electoral processes. The criteria mentioned by Bishop and Hoeffler allow us to evaluate essential aspects such as the structure, responsibilities, organization, and functioning of the EMB. We base our approach on previous international research and classifications, which highlight that the design of electoral management in Romania falls under the independent model. This model assumes that the EMB operates autonomously from political and administrative influences, possessing the necessary authority to administer electoral processes correctly and efficiently.

The results of this research will contribute to a deeper understanding of the functioning and autonomy of the EMB in Romania, highlighting possible discrepancies between formal and real independence. The conclusions can be used both to advance research in this field and to propose recommendations for improving the legal and institutional framework, with the aim of strengthening democracy and public trust in electoral processes.

The design of the electoral management system in Romania

After 1990, the norm in post-communist countries has been the establishment of an independent electoral authority tasked with organizing and conducting electoral processes in a fair, transparent, and equitable manner. In Romania, this development occurred in 2003, with its effective implementation in the context of the 2004 elections, when the Permanent Electoral Authority (AEP) was established³. Essentially, after 14 years of democratic electoral practice and four rounds of general elections (in 1990, 1992, 1996, and 2000), Romania created an EMB design specific to the independent model.

Prior to this point, the electoral process was managed in a manner more characteristic of the governmental model, with the mention that, before each electoral event, an ad hoc body called the Central Electoral Bureau (BEC), which had independent status and a role in coordinating and supervising the entire electoral process, was constituted. This institution with a special status is still part of the EMB, but within the institutional architecture of electoral domain, it is complemented by the AEP. Over time, with the modification of the legislative framework, the position of the Permanent Electoral Authority within the Romanian EMB has been consolidated, and its responsibilities have been expanded. In essence, by establishing the AEP as a permanent electoral body, Romania transitioned from the governmental model to the independent model for organizing and administering electoral processes.

According to the most comprehensive global comparative data set on electoral management bodies' institutional design (Catt et al, 2014; Wall et al, 2006), Romania uses the *independent model of electoral management*. The characterization of the Romanian system as an independent model is

³ Law no. 286/2003 regarding the amendment and completion of Law no. 68/1992 for the election of the Chamber of Deputies and the Senate.

based on the existence of an institution that is autonomous from the Government, responsible for all aspects of election organization and management, ensuring an impartial and transparent electoral process.

A dualistic electoral management system

The Romanian EMB has a dual formula comprising two bodies to manage elections, both officially independent from the executive. One of these bodies has an ongoing activity, and based on the model, it should play a decision-making role in shaping policies relating to the electoral process. This refers to the Permanent Electoral Authority (AEP). The other has a temporary activity, functioning only within the electoral context, and should be responsible for conducting and implementing the electoral process under legal conditions. This refers to the Central Electoral Bureau (BEC). In practice, in the electoral context, the EMB is the BEC. During the election organization period, the AEP provides technical support, but the decision-making authority in electoral matters belongs to the BEC.

The AEP is an autonomous administrative institution under the authority of the Parliament. It is responsible for the preparation, organization, and conduct of elections and referendums, as well as for supervising the financing of political parties and electoral campaigns.

The AEP oversees the entire electoral process, from candidate registration to the announcement of final results. The institution monitors compliance with regulations, resolves any issues that arise, and ensures that elections are conducted in a transparent and fair manner. Essentially, the AEP is tasked with developing and adopting rules, procedures, and technical measures governing the electoral process. To this end, it issues resolutions, decisions, and instructions. Furthermore, the AEP plans and manages the resources necessary for the conduct of elections, such as the Registry of Polling Stations – a centralized database containing information on the delimitation, numbering, locations, and equipment of polling stations – and the Electoral Registry, an essential tool that contains information about eligible voters. Equally important, the AEP must ensure that all citizens have equal access to vote, implement measures to prevent discrimination, and inform the public about all aspects related to elections.

The leadership of the AEP consists of a president and two vice presidents. The president is appointed by a vote of the Parliament, upon the proposal of parliamentary groups, while the vice presidents are appointed by the President of Romania and the Prime Minister, respectively. Their terms are eight years each and can be renewed only once. The president and vice presidents cannot be members of any political party and must have expertise and experience in legal or administrative fields.

The AEP has its own specialized apparatus, coordinated by the president. The institution proposes the size, organization, and functioning of this apparatus, but the decision is a political one, belonging to the Standing Bureaus of the two Chambers of Parliament. The staff of the AEP's specialized apparatus with the status of senior public servants is appointed through competition, examination, or modification of service relationships. These employees cannot be members of political parties.

Regarding the financial resources of the AEP, they are provided by the Government through the state budget. The AEP prepares its own budget proposal and, with the approval of the Ministry of Finance, submits it to the Government for inclusion in the state budget. The president of the Authority is the chief authorizing officer.

The establishment of this financially dependent institution on the government, which can make electoral proposals but does not effectively decide, and which, during elections, provides

technical support to another institution that ensures the effective management of elections, has conferred the formal independence of the EMB. The AEP has added more complexity to the electoral management system by supplementing the institution that already fulfilled this role. Practically, the BEC continues to operate as a political-legal electoral management institution with a temporary character. The political decision-maker aimed to transform the system, not by replacing the BEC, but by creating another institution with permanent operation and administrative-type duties, thus conferring the dual structure of the EMB. In the electoral context, the role of the AEP diminishes, with the central institution responsible for the concrete organization and validation of election results being the BEC.

Thus, during the election organization period, the BEC and constituency electoral bureaus are formed. The BEC is an independent institution, responsible for ensuring the fairness and legality of the electoral process. The institution ceases its activity within 48 hours from the date of publication of the election results in the Official Gazette of Romania. The main responsibilities of the BEC include ensuring a democratic, fair, and transparent electoral process; guaranteeing citizens' voting rights and the integrity of elections; and centralizing and communicating election results. The BEC receives and resolves any complaints regarding the organization and conduct of elections.

The BEC is composed of five judges from the High Court of Cassation and Justice, the president and vice presidents of the Permanent Electoral Authority, and up to 12 representatives of political parties, political alliances, electoral alliances, and one representative designated by the parliamentary group of national minorities in the Chamber of Deputies. Political actors can designate only one representative to the BEC, but the law discriminates between parliamentary and non-parliamentary political parties, giving priority to parliamentary parties by virtue of the BEC formation calendar⁴. The President of the BEC is elected by vote by the five judges, from among themselves.

The BEC adopts decisions and resolutions by a majority vote of the members present. The resolutions aim to provide a uniform interpretation of the law and are generally binding. The BEC's decisions are intended to implement and ensure compliance with the provisions of the electoral law and to resolve complaints and contestations. The BEC's decisions are mandatory for all public institutions and can be challenged in court (at the High Court of Cassation and Justice). The auxiliary technical apparatus of the BEC is provided by the AEP, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and the National Institute of Statistics.

A critical analysis of the independence of the Romanian EMB

Although the AEP operates continuously to organize the electoral process, in an electoral context, the BEC is the institution responsible for organizing and conducting specific electoral operations. For instance, BEC verifies the compliance with legal conditions and validates candidacies, centralizes votes, determines election results, can order a recount of votes or a review of the vote centralization and results in specific situations, and periodically informs the public about voter turnout, among other duties. The role of AEP is to provide technical support so that BEC can manage all essential elements for the conduct of elections.

Given its temporary nature, BEC is established and operates when elections take place. The entire institutional framework is hierarchical and centralized, encompassing three subsequent levels

⁴ The BEC is completed with a representative from each parliamentary political party within 24 hours of the election of the Bureau's president, and with representatives from non-parliamentary political parties within 24 hours of the definitive standing of the candidacies.

of responsibilities and actions: the central/top level represented by BEC; the intermediary level consisting of constituency (county) electoral bureaus; and the lower level at the base of the hierarchy, belonging to the polling station electoral bureaus. Practically, there is not a single BEC but multiple ones. Because Romania organizes three types of national elections (local, parliamentary, and presidential) and each is governed by distinct electoral laws, the organization and activities of BEC are each time subject to a different law. These laws have common provisions but also differences due to the particularities of the type of election and the level at which they take place, as well as the timing and context in which the legislation was adopted and revised. The lack of unified legislation or an Electoral Code that integrates the three laws, synchronizes their provisions, and ensures the coherence of the entire institutional design creates a fertile ground for confusion, ambiguities, and uncertainties. This issue also impacts the EMB, specifically the BEC.

For instance, the three electoral laws use different names for the electoral management structures. In the case of local elections, the organization and conduct of electoral operations involve the establishment of the BEC, county electoral bureaus, constituency electoral bureaus, and polling station electoral bureaus (art. 25-1). During parliamentary elections, the structures include the BEC, constituency electoral bureaus at the county level, a bureau for the municipality of Bucharest, sector electoral offices (in Bucharest), a constituency electoral bureau for citizens abroad, and polling station electoral bureaus (art. 7-1). For presidential elections, the BEC, county electoral bureaus, sector electoral bureaus in Bucharest, the electoral bureau for polling stations abroad, and polling station electoral bureaus are established (art. 13-1).

Firstly, in the case of the local elections law⁵, there is confusion between the county electoral bureaus and the constituency electoral bureaus. Although the county represents a constituency, the law uses two distinct notions: county electoral bureaus and constituency electoral bureaus. Additionally, for the sectors of Bucharest, only the law for the election of the Chamber of Deputies and the Senate uses the term "electoral office" instead of "electoral bureau."

Although these electoral bureaus are established and operate only during elections, the legislation is not always precise about this timing. For example, the presidential elections law uses the term "electoral period," defined as "the time interval starting on the date of the Government's decision establishing the election date and ending with the publication of the election results in the Official Gazette of Romania." The parliamentary elections law refers to the "election organization period" but also uses the term "electoral period," defined similarly to the presidential elections law. The local elections law includes terms such as "election period" and "electoral period" but does not explicitly define them.

Legislative differences based on the type of elections also exist regarding the numerical composition of the BEC. As a general rule, it consists of a number of judges from the High Court of Cassation and Justice (ÎCCJ), the president and vice-presidents of the AEP, and a number of representatives from parliamentary and, if applicable, non-parliamentary political parties. In parliamentary and presidential elections, the BEC includes five judges, while for local elections, the BEC comprises seven judges. Regarding political actors, their number in the BEC composition varies by election type: up to 12 for parliamentary elections, a maximum of 10 for presidential elections, and a fixed number of 11 for local elections. Political actors can appoint a single representative to the BEC, but the law discriminates, as mentioned earlier, between parliamentary and non-parliamentary political parties.

⁵ For a discussion of the legislation on local elections in 2020, see Buti and Radu (2021).

Regarding the financing of expenses for conducting electoral operations and ensuring the functioning of electoral bureaus, the legislation is relatively uniform, with nuances given by the nature of the elections, establishing responsibilities for both central and local authorities, depending on the political-administrative level in which and for which the elections are conducted. Thus, expenses for organizing national elections (parliamentary and presidential) are covered by the state budget, while local elections are funded by local budgets (communes, cities, municipalities, Bucharest sectors, counties, the municipality of Bucharest). Additionally, the BEC's equipment and expenses are covered by the Government, regardless of the type of election, but for other electoral bureaus (constituency bureaus), funding is shared, being the responsibility of both the Government (through prefects) and local public administration authorities.

The BEC plays a fundamental role in determining election results. The electoral procedure for recording and centralizing voting results is hierarchical, similar across the three types of elections, but with particularities given by their nature, the electoral system used, and the rules that translate votes into seats.

Formal independence vs. functional independence

The analysis of the roles and responsibilities of the two institutions comprising the Romanian EMB leads to an interim conclusion that the electoral management exhibits formal independence from the government and political actors. The existence of the AEP, the recruitment and appointment of its leadership and staff, and its electoral responsibilities confer a degree of independence to the electoral management system.

In practice, however, the Romanian EMB model is more governmental in nature. Firstly, maintaining the BEC within the institutional architecture argues against EMB independence. BEC is a temporary institution composed of representatives from political parties, playing a decisive role in the organization and conduct of elections. During elections, BEC holds a preeminent status over AEP, being directly responsible for election organization, result centralization, and dispute resolution. Given its political composition, its decisions are sometimes publicly reflected upon and commented on in a political key⁶, and even contested in court. Although BEC is designed to be an impartial and independent body, perceptions of political influence may arise due to the nature of its decisions and the political context in which it operates.

Secondly, despite formal independence, the government plays a significant role in electoral management. Financial resources are a critical factor in EMB independence, and in Romania, AEP's funding is provided by the government. In the absence of autonomous financing, independent of the annual government budget, legal guarantees ensuring a mandatory minimum budget, or an independent financial oversight body, government funding of AEP can affect its independence, as control over financial resources can be used as a means of political influence.

Furthermore, the Romanian EMB has no role in setting the electoral calendar. This is an exclusive attribute of the government, with consultations between AEP and the government being strictly formal. Specifically, the Romanian Government issues a decision that establishes the election date and details of the electoral calendar, including deadlines for various stages of the electoral

⁶ These perceptions often arise in the context of controversial decisions or during tense electoral moments when the interpretation and application of electoral legislation can favor or disadvantage certain political parties or candidates. For instance, during electoral campaigns, decisions regarding the validation or invalidation of candidacies are frequently contested and publicized, fueling discussions about potential political influence.

process (submission of candidacies, electoral campaign, voting, etc.). Practically, if the government has exclusive control over setting the electoral calendar, there is a risk that decisions may be influenced by political considerations, thereby affecting the independence of the EMB.

It should also be noted that the legal requirement that the president and vice-presidents of the AEP cannot be members of a political party is largely formal. The law does not impose time limits on prior political affiliations, allowing a politician to become president of the AEP the day after renouncing party membership. Moreover, the appointment process for the president and vice-presidents of the AEP is subject to political decisions, which can result in the selection of individuals who, while not party members, have informal political sympathies or affiliations (Radu, 2005). This undermines the law's intention to ensure apolitical leadership. The current president of the AEP exemplifies this situation, having previously held the position of prefect, a government representative in the territory, and being a former member of one of the governing parties that proposed him for the AEP leadership⁷. This is a classic example of the difference between formal institutional reality and functional reality, between adhering to the letter of the law and its spirit, or more simply, an example of a form (legal provision) without substance (circumventing it in practice). This can affect public perception and, consequently, the credibility of the AEP. If there are suspicions that the president and vice-presidents have political connections, even informal ones, this perception can negatively impact trust in the institution's independence and impartiality.

Additionally, the AEP and BEC are not the only institutions with responsibilities in the electoral process, particularly in its technical-administrative dimension. Through prefects, the government is part of this process. Although prefects do not have a direct decision-making role, they have essential administrative and logistical responsibilities for the smooth conduct of elections. For instance, according to the law governing the election of the Senate and the Chamber of Deputies, prefects ensure, in collaboration with other local and/or central authorities, inter-institutional communication, the production and distribution of electoral materials (ballots, stamps, other necessary voting materials), informing citizens about the delimitation and numbering of polling stations and voting rules, public order and safety, etc. By providing the necessary infrastructure and logistical coordination, prefectures contribute to creating an environment conducive to the proper and efficient conduct of the electoral process. This involvement must be neutral and impartial to maintain public trust in the integrity of elections, but it gives the government a role, even if marginal, within the EMB framework. All these factors indicate that the independence of the Romanian EMB is formal. In reality, the government holds a significant position within the institutional electoral management system, having direct or indirect levers to play an active role in the electoral process. This makes the electoral management model a disguised governmental one. At the first level of formal analysis, it appears independent, being built around the AEP. In practice, however, independence is limited, with the government and the political majority having areas of decision and influence.

Evolution of the independence and impartiality of the EMB

To strengthen our analytical observations and gain a more comprehensive view of the independence of the Romanian EMB, it is useful to evaluate this system using the criteria formulated by Bishop and Hoeffler (2016). The five criteria help transition from a formal analysis, based on institutional criteria and norms, principles, duties, and responsibilities provided by law, to a functional analysis of political

⁷ The two vice-presidents of AEP are in the same situation, this being the informal rule for appointing the management of this institution.

and institutional practice, based on real-world conditions. They provide an in-depth view of the degree of independence, impartiality, and legal compliance of EMB, as well as its capacity to organize fair and transparent elections, without undue political interference. We will refer to the specific conditions of the parliamentary elections in Romania.

Election boundaries are set up so that no candidate/party is favored (no gerrymandering) (de facto) This criterion is less relevant in the case of Romania, given the proportional representation (PR) system used for parliamentary elections⁸ and the fact that the delineation of electoral constituencies is regulated by the electoral law. Thus, since 1990, for the organization of elections in post-communist Romania, electoral constituencies have been established at the level of the 41 counties⁹, one constituency in Bucharest, and later, a constituency for Romanian citizens abroad¹⁰. The same electoral law also sets the representation norm, i.e., the number of citizens represented by a parliamentarian (deputy or senator)¹¹, a basic criterion for the district magnitude and the total number of MPs. In practice, the election boundaries have great stability, with the decision regarding them belonging to Parliament, not to the institutions comprising the EMB. The latter, specifically the AEP, have the role of monitoring the delimitation of polling stations and proposing the establishment of new polling stations. However, the decision does not belong to them.

There are, however, two exceptions or, rather, two particular cases that nuance the conclusion of the irrelevance of this criterion, without nullifying it. The first refers to an element of the electoral system that conditions access to the legislature, namely the electoral threshold, more precisely the alternative electoral threshold. The value of the electoral threshold is 5%¹², but an alternative threshold of 20% of the total valid votes cast in at least four electoral constituencies also operates. This second threshold is justified by the existence of local/regional parties, but in reality, such political actors lack political and electoral relevance, so the alternative threshold works in favor of a single political formation – the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania (UDMR) – whose votes are sufficiently geographically concentrated to ensure at least 20% of the total valid votes cast in four electoral constituencies/counties.

The second case is that of the so-called "uninominal vote" law, which was in effect for the 2008 and 2012 parliamentary elections and maintained the PR system, including the proportional methods previously used, but associated it with voting in single-member electoral units. Specifically, the existing electoral constituencies were divided into single-member districts¹³, their delineation being done

⁸ For further details, see Radu, A. and Buti, D. (2015) *Postcommunismul românesc. Sistemul politic: structură și funcționare* [Romanian Post-Communism. The Political System: Structure and Functioning]. Bucharest: Pro Universitaria.

⁹ The delimitation of constituencies at the level of administrative-territorial units also applies to local elections.

¹⁰ Introduced by Law no. 35/2008 and maintained in Law no. 208/2015.

¹¹ The representation norm for the election of the Chamber of Deputies is one deputy per 73,000 inhabitants, and for the election of the Senate, it is one senator per 168,000 inhabitants.

¹² In the case of political alliances and electoral alliances, 3% of the valid votes cast nationwide are added to the 5% threshold for the second member of the alliance, and for each additional member of the alliance starting from the third, an additional 1% of the valid votes cast nationwide is added, without exceeding 10% of these votes.

¹³ For further details, see Giugăl et al (2020) "Reforming An Electoral System - An Experiment That Failed: Romania 2008–2012", *Representation*, 56(1), pp. 111-126.

based on rules expressly provided by the electoral law. The same law stipulated that the first delineation of the single-member districts would be carried out by the Government, according to the decision of a special parliamentary committee, with the updating of the districts to be done later by the AEP, after each population census. Therefore, with the mention of its low relevance for the Romanian case, this criterion can be considered met, but only at a formal level.

EMBs are held accountable to election law and abide by it

In Romania, the independence of the EMB, specifically AEP and BEC, aligns with international standards of accountability and adherence to election law. The activities of these two institutions are regulated by law, and they are held accountable to election law. According to the electoral law, AEP operates in accordance with the principles of independence, impartiality, legality, transparency, efficiency, professionalism, responsibility, sustainability, predictability, and legitimacy.

Formally, AEP ensures the transparency of its activities by regularly publishing its budget, financial statements, activity reports, and election results. It also organizes consultations with civil society to improve the electoral system and is obligated to present a report to Parliament on the organization and conduct of elections and referendums. AEP responds to questions and interpellations from parliamentarians.

Practically, the legal framework governing AEP supports its autonomy, allowing it to operate independently. This positioning aligns with comprehensive comparative guides that classify it as independent from the executive branch of government, which is a crucial criterion for ensuring impartiality and credibility in the electoral process. We can consider this criterion to be satisfied.

EMBs are independent and impartial

As observed from the analysis of the roles and responsibilities of the two institutions that comprise the Romanian EMB, electoral management has formal independence from the government and political actors. The existence of the AEP, its recruitment and appointment processes for leadership and staff, as well as its responsibilities, confer a degree of independence to the electoral management system. However, the government controls the institution's funding, sets the electoral calendar, and has a role in the electoral process through the prefects. Additionally, the leadership of the AEP may have prior political affiliations. Moreover, the existence of the BEC, which includes representatives from political parties and plays a decisive role in elections, reduces the EMB's independence. Therefore, the Romanian EMB model has a distinctly governmental imprint. These factors question the existence of genuine independence and impartiality.

Although the formal structure suggests independence, in practice, the government and political majority have mechanisms to influence the electoral process. This makes the electoral management model essentially a covert governmental one, thus limiting the real independence of the EMB. In the words of Goodwin-Gill (2006), the election machinery is "balanced," not impartial. Thus, the Romanian EMB meets this criterion only at a formal level; in reality, its impartiality is compromised by political influence.

EMBs have sufficient time to organize elections (i.e. no snap election)

This is a criterion that the Romanian EMB meets. According to the law, the election date is set by the government and announced to the public at least 90 days before the voting day (through publication in the Official Gazette).

The bicameral Parliament benefits from exceptional stability, meaning that Romania has not experienced the dissolution of Parliament before the end of its term. The primary cause of this reality is found in the provisions of Article 89 of the Constitution, which makes the dissolution of Parliament almost impossible, or more precisely, impossible under normal political conditions. Formally attributed to the head of state, this presidential prerogative can only be exercised when a series of cumulative conditions are met. Thus, "after consultation with the presidents of both Chambers and the leaders of the parliamentary groups, the President of Romania may dissolve Parliament if no vote of confidence has been obtained to form a government within 60 days after the first request was made, and only after the rejection of at least two requests for investiture".

Practically, the President of Romania can dissolve Parliament, without having the obligation to do so, under specific conditions that do not depend exclusively on his will. In fact, these conditions are those accompanying a severe political crisis, in which the country is no longer governed. In such a situation, the only solution can be a snap election. Therefore, by imposing special conditions for the dissolution of Parliament, the fundamental law has drastically restricted the possibility of using this procedure. All this makes the dissolution of Parliament in Romania almost impossible.

Thus, from a formal and rather narrow perspective, regarding the existence or non-existence of snap elections, this criterion is met, but this is not really due to the electoral management system, but to the constitutional norm that makes early parliamentary elections almost impossible.

Decisions made by and complaints made to the EMBs are subject to review and possible reversal

This is a criterion that the Romanian EMB meets. According to the legislation, there are clear procedures by which the decisions of the AEP and the BEC can be contested in court or through other legal mechanisms. This ensures that decisions made are correct and comply with electoral legislation, allowing any abuse or error to be corrected.

With a pyramidal structure, where the base is represented by the electoral bureaus of the polling stations and the apex is the BEC, complaints concerning the activities and decisions of the electoral bureaus are submitted to and resolved by the electoral body constituted at the immediate superior level to which the bureau referred to in the complaint operates, or by the High Court of Cassation and Justice if the complaint concerns the BEC. In an electoral context, all complaints are analyzed and resolved expeditiously.

In the case of the AEP, its decisions can be contested administratively or in court. Complaints can address aspects related to the organization of elections, such as the delimitation of polling stations, electoral lists, or voting procedures, as well as the financing of electoral campaigns and compliance with the norms regarding the financing of political parties. The AEP has supervisory responsibilities in this domain, and its decisions can be contested by political parties or candidates. The AEP periodically publishes reports on its activities, including the complaints received and how they were resolved.

The analysis of the Romanian EMB through the lens of the standards for free and fair elections (Bishop and Hoeffler, 2016) indicates that two out of five criteria are fully satisfied (EMB is held accountable to election law and abides by it; decisions made by and complaints made to the EMB are subject to review and possible reversal), two are only formally respected (election boundaries are set up so that no candidate/party is favored – no gerrymandering; EMB has sufficient time to organize elections), and one is not met (EMB is independent and impartial). Practically, the Romanian electoral management system partially meets the criteria of independence and impartiality, with the potential for governmental/political influences, which limits its real autonomy.

The Romanian EMB – a dualist and mixed system

The analysis of the electoral management authorities in Romania, specifically the AEP and the BEC, has highlighted several critical aspects regarding their functional independence. Although Romania has formally adopted the independent EMB model similar to other democratic states, in reality, this model is more governmental, masked under the appearance of institutional autonomy.

The existence of a dual structure in the institutional mechanism of electoral management – with the AEP having a permanent role and the BEC a temporary role – creates the appearance of formal independence. Firstly, the AEP, by its very institutional nature and assigned responsibilities, should ensure a transparent and fair electoral process. However, the AEP's funding depends on the government, which questions its ability to function truly independently. In the absence of complete financial autonomy and, possibly, legal guarantees ensuring a mandatory minimum budget, control over financial resources remains a lever of political influence over the AEP. Furthermore, the appointment process of AEP leadership is susceptible to political influences. Although legislation stipulates that these positions cannot be held by political party members, there are no clear limits on prior political affiliations. Thus, appointing individuals with informal political sympathies or affiliations undermines the law's intent to ensure apolitical leadership.

Secondly, the BEC, though designed as a temporary and independent body, includes representatives of political parties. This aspect introduces a degree of political influence in the BEC's decision-making processes, affecting public perception of its impartiality. BEC decisions, theoretically neutral, can be contested and perceived as having a political undertone, thereby diminishing trust in the fairness of the elections.

Another problematic aspect is the government's control over the electoral calendar. Setting the election date and the details of the electoral timetable is the exclusive attribute of the government, and consultations with the AEP are strictly formal and non-decisive. This allows the government to manipulate the electoral calendar based on political considerations, impacting the independence of the electoral process.

The evaluation according to the criteria proposed by Bishop and Hoeffler (2016) indicates that the Romanian EMB only partially meets the criteria of independence and impartiality. Two out of five criteria are fully satisfied, two are formally met, and one is not respected. This reflects a discrepancy between the formal and functional independence of the EMB, which moves it away from the independent model.

Therefore, what characterizes the EMB in Romania is, on the one hand, the BEC-AEP institutional dualism, and on the other hand, its proximity to the mixed model, for which it advocates the formal independence of decision-making institutions.

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